

Association of Vitamin D with Microvascular Complications among the Cases of Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Case Control StudySunil Kumar Garg¹, Neelima Hemkar², Mamta Singh*³, Sanjay Kumawat⁴¹3rd Year Resident, Department of Biochemistry, S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan²Senior Professor, Department of Biochemistry, S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan³Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan⁴Senior Demonstrator, Department of Biochemistry, S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Vitamin D has a huge impact on human health and disease. It plays an important role in glucose homeostasis by promoting insulin secretion and reducing resistance. Vitamin D insufficiency may increase the occurrence and progression of type-2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) and its associated complications.**Objectives:** The present study aims to compare vitamin D levels in type-2 diabetes mellitus patients with and without microvascular complications and also to investigate the relationship between vitamin D insufficiency and T2DM microvascular consequences.**Material & Methods:** A case control study was conducted on 60 type-2 diabetes mellitus patients, aged between 40-70 years, as per inclusion and exclusion criteria and divided into 2 groups. **Group-I:** T2DM patients with microvascular complications (n=30) served as study group; and **Group II:** T2DM patients without microvascular complications (n=30) used as control group. Venous blood samples were collected using aseptic techniques. Fasting blood sugar, glycosylated haemoglobin (HbA1c), post prandial blood sugar and vitamin D levels were measured. The collected data were analyzed using student "t" test for evaluating the differences between both groups in reference to above parameters. Pearson correlation analysis was used to find out association of vitamin D levels with glycaemic control (blood sugar and HbA1C levels). The results were expressed as Mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD).**Results:** Vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency was found to be significantly higher in T2DM patients with microvascular complications (14.51 ± 3.79 vs 19.80 ± 5.02) as compared with T2DM patients without microvascular complications ($p < 0.01$). Vitamin D insufficiency was found to be more common in females than males (10.52 ± 1.59 vs 16.50 ± 2.77 ; $p < 0.001$). Vitamin D level also shows statistically significant negative correlation with HbA1C ($r = -0.887$, $p < 0.001$); fasting blood sugar (FBS) $r = -0.901$, $p < 0.001$; and 2 hour post prandial blood sugar (PPBS) $r = -0.583$, $p < 0.001$ and prevalence of microvascular complications.**Conclusion:** Vitamin D insufficiency is significantly associated with glycaemic control and with any of the individual microvascular complications, i.e. neuropathy, retinopathy, and nephropathy. Therefore, early screening for vitamin D levels in T2DM patients may be beneficial due to the diverse implications of vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency. Estimation and correction of vitamin D deficiency may also help in prevention of microvascular complications.**Keywords:** Type 2 diabetes mellitus, Vitamin D, Microvascular complications, Glycaemic control.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Diabetes mellitus is a severe and major public health concern with a substantial economic burden worldwide. As per International Diabetes Federation (IDF) reports, currently 537 million adults are living with diabetes and projected to rise to 783 million by 2045 without urgent and sufficient actions [1]. Diabetes has steadily increased in India and around the world over the last three decades. India accounts for a sizable

portion of the global burden and ranks second after China in the global diabetes epidemic with 77 million people with diabetes. It is one of the world's fastest growing chronic disease and leading cause of death globally. More than 90% of diabetes mellitus are type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) [2]. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a group of clinical syndromes characterized by long-term hyperglycaemia causing chronic complications in

multiple organs. In T2DM, the main microvascular complications are diabetic retinopathy (DR), diabetic nephropathy (DN), and diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN). All of which have profound adverse impact on patient's quality of life and lead to disability or mortality [3-6]. Despite increasing knowledge regarding risk factors and prevention programs for type 2 diabetes, the incidence and prevalence of the disease and its complications continues to rise globally [7-8]. The mechanism behind development of complications to diabetes are only partly understood and the search for additional modifiable risk factors is essential to reduce the burdensome complications.

Vitamin D is a multifunctional fat-soluble micronutrient, that has gained enormous interest for potential extra skeletal outcomes in various disease conditions, including diabetes. It is mainly synthesized in skin by UVB irradiation of 7-dehydrocholesterol, while ergosterol is derived from the diet (primarily from mushrooms and fungi) and converted to pre-vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol). Both are hydroxylated to 25(OH)D₃ and 25(OH)D₂, respectively by multiple 25-hydroxylases in the liver [9]. 25(OH)D is converted to active 1,25(OH)₂D by 1- α -hydroxylase present not only in renal tubular cells but also in many cells such as macrophages, adipocytes and pancreatic beta cells [10].

Vitamin D can exert its various physiological effects through binding to its specific receptor, vitamin D receptor (VDR). In addition to mediating bone metabolism (by regulating calcium and phosphorus homeostasis), vitamin D also modulates cell proliferation and differentiation, apoptosis, immune function, inflammation response, as well as vascular and metabolic properties [11-13]. Vitamin D can play a major role in glucose homeostasis by improving insulin secretion and sensitivity and reducing resistance. Moreover, vitamin D is involved in stimulation of neurotrophic factors like nerve growth factor, glial cell line derived neurotrophic factor and suppression of RAAS, reduction of albuminuria, immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory and antiangiogenic effects [14-16].

In recent years, vitamin D insufficiency has been implicated in the occurrence and progression of diabetes and its complications (i.e. retinopathy, neuropathy and nephropathy). Emerging evidences support association between inadequate level of vitamin D and poor glycaemic management, which may cause a further exacerbation of the microvascular complications of T2DM [17].

However, there is a paucity of Indian research on the origins of vascular problems of diabetes caused by a lack of 25-hydroxyvitamin D. Therefore, we conducted this study to compare the levels of

vitamin D in T2DM patients with microvascular complication and without microvascular complications and also to investigate the relationship between vitamin D insufficiency and T2DM microvascular consequences.

Materials and Methods

After taking necessary permission from the Institutional Ethical Committee, the present study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry (Central Lab and Immunoassay Lab) and Endocrinology OPD, SMS Medical College and Attached Hospitals, Jaipur. This study was a hospital-based case control study and sampling for the study was done from period of January 2023 to June 2024. An informed written consent was obtained from all study participants. A total 60 patients suffering from type 2 diabetes mellitus participated in the study. Detailed personal and clinical history of all subjects were recorded with the help of a questionnaire. Clinical examination was carried out by a competent Endocrinologists. The subjects were categorized into 2 groups:

Group I: Cases/ Study Group (n = 30); Type 2 diabetes mellitus patients with microvascular complications were considered as cases.

Group II: Control Group (n = 30); Type 2 diabetes mellitus patients without microvascular complications were taken as control.

Inclusion Criteria:

Cases

Individuals attending OPD of Endocrinology Department, SMS Hospital, Jaipur, having type 2 diabetes mellitus with microvascular complications (such as diabetic nephropathy, diabetic retinopathy, and diabetic peripheral neuropathy etc.), aged between 40-70 years, those who were willing to participate and given written informed consent for the study were included in the study.

Controls

Age and sex matched patients of type 2 diabetes mellitus without microvascular complications who were willing to participate in the study and given written consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

Patients of age below 40 years and above 70 years, suffering from any parathyroid disorder, taking Calcium and Vitamin D supplements, type 1 diabetic patients, patients with any febrile disease including tuberculosis, pregnant and lactating women were excluded.

Sample Collection:

Venous blood samples were collected into appropriate vials after overnight fast (8-12 hours)

for estimation of Vitamin D and routine biochemistry parameters (plain vial), fasting and post prandial blood sugar (sodium fluoride vial) and EDTA vial for HbA1c Assay. Grossly hemolyzed and lipaemic samples were excluded.

Biochemical Analysis:

About 3 mL of venous blood was collected from the antecubital vein in fasting condition by aseptic techniques into appropriate vials. Samples were centrifuged after 30 minutes, serum was separated and used for the measurement of following parameters-

- Blood glucose was assayed by GOD-POD method and Glycosylated haemoglobin (HbA1C) was measured by Latex Turbidimetric assay in Central Lab on fully automated clinical chemistry analyzer Beckman Coulter AU5811.
- 25-Hydroxy vitamin D (25-OHD) was measured by chemiluminescence Immuno-Assay method in Immunoassay Lab on ADIA Centaur XP Immunoassay Analyzer.

- Expected Values of Vitamin D: Deficiency <20 ng/mL; Insufficiency 20-<30 ng/mL; Sufficiency 30-100 ng/mL

Statistical Analysis

All the relevant demographic, clinical and laboratory data were entered into Microsoft Office Excel sheet, and the data were then collected on primer software for statistical analysis. Continuous data were summarized in form of means and standard deviation.

Differences in two mean was analyzed using student t test. Categorical data were expressed in form of proportion or percentage. Difference in proportion was analyzed using chi square test.

A level of significance was kept 75% for all statistical analysis. Pearson's correlation analysis was applied to determine the relationship between Vitamin D and HbA1c, FBS, PPBS. Statistical significance was defined at $p < 0.05$.

Observation Table

Table 1: Gender wise distribution of study participants

Parameters	Controls (T2DM without Complications)	Cases (T2DM with Complications)
Total No. of cases	30	30
Male: Female	20:10	20:10
%	67:33	67:33

Table 2: Baseline characteristics of study participants

Parameters	Controls (T2DM without Complications) (n=30)	Cases (T2DM with Complications) (n=30)	P-value
Age (years)	58.27 ± 7.01	57.90 ± 8.04	0.425 (NS)
FBS (mg/dL)	131.53 ± 12.87	163.10 ± 18.87	<0.01(S)
PPBS (mg/dL)	161.93 ± 11.80	180.87 ± 15.88	<0.01(S)
HbA1c (%)	7.17 ± 0.41	8.62 ± 0.72	<0.01(S)
Duration of Diabetes in (years)	3.05 ± 0.38	6.45 ± 0.54	<0.001 (S)

Values are Mean ± SD; *p-value as obtained on applying students't-test

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Vitamin D levels between Controls and Cases Group

Parameter	Controls (T2DM without Complications) (n=30)	Cases (T2DM with Complications) (n=30)	p-value
Vitamin D (ng/ml)	19.80 ± 5.02	14.51 ± 3.79	< 0.01 (S)

Values are Mean ± SD; *p-value as obtained on applying students't-test

Figure 1: Comparison of Mean Vitamin D levels between Controls (T2DM without Complications) and Cases (T2DM with Complications)

Table 4: Comparison of Mean Vitamin D levels in Males and Females

Parameter	Males (T2DM with Complications) (n=20)	Females (T2DM with Complications) (n=10)	p-value
Vitamin D (ng/ml)	16.50 ± 2.77	10.52 ± 1.59	< 0.001 (S)

Table 5: Correlation between Vitamin D and HBA1c in Type 2 DM patients with complications

Parameter	R Score	R ²	p- Value
Vitamin D vs HBA1c	-0.8874	0.7875	P<0.001*(S)

Data analysis using Pearson correlation analysis *

Figure 2: Correlation between Vitamin D and HBA1c in Type 2 DM patients with complications

Table 6: Correlation between Vitamin D and Blood Sugar in Type 2 DM patients with complications

Parameter	R Score	R ²	P value
Vitamin D vs FBS	-0.9013	0.8123	<0.001*(S)
Vitamin D vs PPBS	-0.5836	0.3406	<0.001*(S)

*Data analysis using Pearson correlation analysis

Figure 3: Correlation between Vitamin D and blood sugar in Type 2 DM patients with complications

Results

Table-1 shows gender wise distribution of study participants. Male cases and female cases were 67% and 33% amongst control and the case groups. This was done to maintain matching amongst cases and controls and to eliminate any kind of bias in the study on the basis of gender.

Table-2 displays baseline characteristics of study subjects. The mean age in control group was 58.27 ± 7.01 years which was slightly higher than cases group (57.90 ± 8.04 years). This difference was statistically not significant (p -value=0.4256). Controls were matched in this respect.

The mean fasting blood sugar level for cases was 163.10 ± 18.87 mg/dl and that for controls was 131.53 ± 12.87 mg/dl. Mean 2-hours postprandial blood sugar level for cases and controls was 180.87 ± 15.88 vs 161.93 ± 11.80 mg/dl respectively. Both FBS and PPBS were significantly higher in cases group (p value < 0.01).

In cases, mean HbA1c level was 8.62 ± 0.72 % and in controls 7.17 ± 0.41 % which was statistically higher in cases group (p value < 0.01) representing more poor glycaemic control in type 2 DM patients with microvascular complications. Duration of diabetes was more in cases group than controls.

Table-3 represents comparison of mean vitamin D levels in both study groups. In cases vitamin D level was 19.80 ± 5.02 ng/ml and in control 14.51 ± 3.79 ng/ml which was significantly lower in cases as compared to controls (p value < 0.01) (Fig No.1). In gender wise comparison vitamin D insufficiency was more common in females than age matched males (10.52 ± 1.59 vs 16.50 ± 2.77 ; $p < 0.001$) (Table-4). Table-5 and fig no.2 shows statistically significant negative correlation

between vitamin D and HbA1c levels in type 2 DM cases with microvascular complications ($r = -0.8874$; $p < 0.001$). Similarly, vitamin D also have negative correlation with fasting blood sugar ($r = -0.9013$, $p < 0.001$) and post prandial blood sugar ($r = -0.5836$, $p < 0.001$) in Type 2 DM cases with Microvascular Complications (Table-6 and fig no.3).

Discussion

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus is a common, chronic metabolic disease with complex causes and pathogenesis. A number of risk factors that increase the risk for the disease and its complications have been identified, including modifiable risk factors (body mass index (BMI), physical inactivity, diet) and nonmodifiable risk factors (age, ethnicity, comorbid diseases, family history and genetic predisposition). Recent studies observed that vitamin D can reduce the occurrence of diabetes and delay the progression of its complications and can reduce oxidative stress, inhibit iron apoptosis, promote insulin secretion and reduce insulin resistance [18-20]. Evidence is limited regarding the associations between vitamin D status and microvascular complication in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus. Therefore, the purpose of the present study was to determine the status of vitamin D and its relation with glycaemic control and its role in microvascular complication in T2DM with and without microvascular complications.

In our study we found that decreased level of vitamin D was severe in T2DM patients with microvascular complications than without complications. Moreover, a significant inverse correlation was observed between glycosylated haemoglobin and vitamin D levels suggesting that

vitamin D may have role in regulation of glucose in T2DM. Most of our study subjects that had microvascular complications had vitamin D insufficiency. In a recent study Ahmed Lina HM et al [21] also observed an inverse association between vitamin D levels and prevalence of microvascular complications. Similarly, Scragg R et al [22] found lower concentration of vitamin D in females than males and pointed out that lower level of vitamin D may increase the risk of diabetes.

In a double-blinded placebo trial, Mitri et al [23] found that in adults at risk of T2DM, short-term supplementation with cholecalciferol improved beta cell function and had a marginal effect on attenuating the rise in HbA1c. Furthermore, studies by Hutchinson MS et al [24] and Zoppini G et al [25] had shown an inverse relationship of 25(OH)D with HbA1c in subjects with and without diabetes. Devaraj S et al [26] observed that the first quartile of serum 25(OH)D level, compared with the fourth quartile, was associated with an increased adjusted odds ratio (OR) for prediabetes and vitamin D levels were inversely correlated with fasting glucose ($r=-0.29$, $P = 0.04$) and homeostasis model assessment (HOMA) ($r = -0.34$, $P = 0.04$).

In a meta-analysis Pittas AG et al [27] reported that vitamin D deficiency was common in diabetic patients, and diabetic complications could be delayed or prevented by vitamin D supplementation. A study by Suzuki A et al [28] on 581 Japanese patients with T2DM found an inverse, significant association between serum 25(OH)D levels and the number of microvascular complications. Vitamin D deficiency was also associated with self-reported peripheral neuropathy symptoms in relatively small samples of patients with T2DM [29-30]. Similarly, study by Zhao WJ et al [31] found that vitamin D deficiency is independently associated with higher risk of diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) and diabetic nephropathy (DN) in T2DM patients and further suggest that vitamin D may be a potential predictor for both the occurrence and severity of DPN and DN.

Recent studies had proved various pleiotropic effects of vitamin D i.e. insulin secretion and insulin sensitivity, cell proliferation and differentiation, apoptosis, immune function and inflammatory responses, besides its traditional role in bone metabolism [11–13]. Vitamin D receptor and alpha 1 hydroxylase enzyme are highly dense in many tissues (on pancreatic beta cells, adipose tissue, skeletal muscles). Vitamin D can regulate glucose metabolism by promoting insulin exocytosis, by stimulating insulin receptor directly, by decreasing insulin resistance and by improving glucose uptake in peripheral tissues. Studies revealed that the insulin receptor gene promoter

contains a vitamin D sensitive element. By regulating the production and activity of cytokines, vitamin D can reduce systemic inflammation. It also has immune regulating actions [32-34].

Similar to our findings, other studies also suggest that lower 25 (OH)D levels and microvascular complications (principally diabetic retinopathy and nephropathy) are strictly inter-related. However, whether low vitamin D status is the cause or result of the presence of microvascular complications is presently unknown required longitudinal studies.

Conclusion

We concluded that mean Vitamin D levels are significantly lower in T2DM patients with microvascular complications. Vitamin D insufficiency is significantly associated with glycaemic control and with any of the individual microvascular complications, i.e. neuropathy, retinopathy, and nephropathy. Therefore, early screening for vitamin D levels in T2DM patients may be beneficial due to the diverse implications of vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency. Estimation and correction of vitamin D deficiency may also help in prevention of microvascular complications. Nevertheless, the relationship between vitamin D and diabetic complications as well as the pathogenesis involved needs further longitudinal investigations.

Limitations

This study was an observational study from a single tertiary care center; confounders like diet and physical activity were not included

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